

CLONING OF RECOMBINANT PURINE NUCLEOSIDE PHOSPHORYLASE IN *E. COLI*

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Abstract. Purine nucleoside phosphorylase is a key enzyme in the metabolism of purine nucleosides. It catalyzes the reversible phosphorolytic cleavage of glycosidic bonds in both ribonucleosides and deoxyribonucleosides, forming purine bases in combination with ribose-1-phosphate or deoxyribose-1-phosphate. The high capacity for enzymatic trans-glycosylation of PNP from *E. coli* is of particular interest in biotechnology for the production of biologically active nucleoside analogues. In this work, we describe the construction of a recombinant plasmid DNA - pET-28a(+)-PNP (6070 bp), containing the PNP gene (728 bp) for expression of this enzyme in *E. coli*.

Keywords: enzymatic hydrolysis, *Escherichia coli*, modified nucleosides, nucleoside phosphorylases, PNP.

Introduction. Nucleoside phosphorylases (NPs) are widely used in the synthesis of modified nucleosides with strong therapeutic potential for the treatment of cancer, viral infections, and bacterial diseases. [1-2, 6] These enzymes are divided into two main categories based on substrate preference: purine nucleoside phosphorylases (PNPs, EC 2.4.2.1) and pyrimidine nucleoside phosphorylases (PyNPs, EC 2.4.2.2). Both types perform the same function, namely catalyzing the reversible phosphorylation reactions of nucleosides, generating nucleobases and α -D-pentofuranose-1-phosphate. [3–5] Compared with traditional chemical synthesis, enzymatic methods provide enhanced selectivity and efficiency, especially for site-directed transglycosylation reactions. Among them, PNPs from *E. coli* have become particularly popular in the biosynthesis of purine-based nucleoside analogues. [6–10] The use of recombinant enzymes as crude lysates or purified proteins has been significantly advanced by genetic engineering techniques. *Escherichia coli* remain one of the most widely used hosts for recombinant protein production due to its rapid growth, genetic transmissibility, and high productivity. This study aimed to design and clone a plasmid that can drive high-level expression of recombinant PNP in *E. coli*, creating a scalable system suitable for industrial enzyme production [11].

The aim of this study was to clone a recombinant plasmid pET-28a(+)-PNP suitable for the expression of recombinant purine nucleoside phosphorylase in *Escherichia coli* cells in order to develop a high-throughput system suitable for industrial production.

Materials and methods. The pET-28a(+) vector was obtained from Novagen (Cat.No. 69864-3), while restriction enzymes EcoRI, NotI, and T4 DNA ligase were sourced from Invitrogen (Thermo Scientific, USA). All other reagents used in the experiments were of analytical grade and supplied by Sigma-Aldrich (Germany). The PNP gene was amplified using the

recombinant plasmid pPICZ α A-PNP, available from the Laboratory of Molecular Genetics at ICPS, Republic of Uzbekistan.

Preparation of transfer vector pET-28a (+) and cDNA (gene) of PNP

Bacterial cultures containing the pET-28a(+) plasmid and target cDNA were grown in LB Broth Miller (Invitrogen) for 12 h at 37°C. To isolate cDNA, 1 ml of the overnight culture was transferred to a 1.5 ml microcentrifuge tube and centrifuged at high speed for 1 min. The supernatant was removed and the pellet was resuspended in 600 μ l of lysis buffer consisting of 9.34 ml TE buffer (pH 8), 600 μ l 10% SDS, and 60 μ l proteinase K (20 mg/ml). The mixture was vortexed and incubated at 37°C for one hour.

Cell lysates were subjected to two rounds of phenol/chloroform extraction followed by a final extraction with chloroform alone. After centrifugation, the aqueous phase was carefully transferred to a clean tube. The DNA was precipitated by adding three volumes of cold 96% ethanol and mixing gently. One microliter of this extracted DNA served as template in a 20 μ l PCR reaction [12].

The pET-28a(+) plasmid (1 μ g) was sequentially digested with EcoRI and NotI restriction enzymes. The resulting linear vector DNA (~5350 bp) was separated by 0.7% agarose gel electrophoresis and purified using the PureLink™ Quick Gel Extraction Kit (Thermo Scientific™). [13]

The approximately 728 base pair long PNP gene (deod) was PCR amplified using specific primers derived from the plasmid pPICZ α A-PNP:

- Forward: 5'- CCAAGAATTCATGGCTACCACACATTAATGC -3'
- Reverse: 5'- CTTGGCGGCCGCTATTACTCTTTTATCGCCAGCA -3'

The amplified product was purified by gel electrophoresis and extracted using the PureLink™ Quick Gel Extraction Kit, followed by digestion with EcoRI and NotI enzymes to generate suitable ends for ligation.

Ligation of the vector with cDNA (PNP gene).

The PNP gene insert was ligated into the linearized pET-28a(+) vector using T4 DNA ligase in a 10 μ l reaction mixture at a 1:4 molar ratio of vector to insert. The reaction was incubated under standard ligation conditions recommended by the enzyme manufacturer. (Fig. 1) [14-15].

Transformation of *E. coli* TOP10 with a ligation mixture

Following ethanol precipitation, the ligation mixture was resuspended in 10 μ l of nuclease-free water. This recombinant DNA was introduced into electrocompetent *E. coli* TOP10 cells via electroporation using the protocol provided by Invitrogen. [16].

Identification of recombinant clones containing pET-28a (+) PNP

After ethanol precipitation, the ligated recombinant DNA was resuspended in 10 μ l of deionized water. This DNA solution was subsequently transformed into electrocompetent, plasmid-free *E. coli* TOP10 cells (Invitrogen) using electroporation, in accordance with the manufacturer's instructions.

Transformation of the pET-28a (+) PNP vector into *E. coli* BL21 DE3

The recombinant plasmid pPICZ α A-PNP was linearized using EcoRI and NotI. The digestion mixture was then subjected to ethanol precipitation in the presence of 3 M sodium acetate (pH 5.2) to purify and concentrate the DNA. The resulting purified linear plasmid was transformed into *E. coli* BL21 (DE3) cells via electroporation using an Electroporator 2510 (Eppendorf, USA).

Transformed cells were subsequently cultured in YPD selective medium supplemented with 100 µg/mL Kanamycin™

Results and Discussion. This study presents the successful construction and molecular cloning of a recombinant plasmid, pET-28a(+)-PNP, designed to express purine nucleoside phosphorylase (PNP) from the opportunistic *E. coli* strain RKMUz-221. PNP is known to catalyze the reversible phosphorolysis of nucleosides in the presence of inorganic phosphate, and to cleave glycosidic bonds in ribose or deoxyribose sugars [10-11]. Among the available expression systems, *Escherichia coli* is considered to be very efficient for large-scale recombinant protein production due to its rapid growth and ability to produce large amounts of target proteins [12]. The final recombinant plasmid, pET-28a(+)-PNP, is 6070 base pairs long and is derived from the pET-28a(+) expression vector, which is approximately 5369 bp in size. This vector is specifically designed for protein expression in *E. coli* and contains elements such as a T7 promoter, a kanamycin resistance gene, and multiple cloning sites.

Fig. 1. Physical map of the recombinant plasmid pET-28a(+)-PNP (6070 bp) is shown below.

Ligation of pET-28a(+) vector with cDNA (PNP gene) and transformation of *E. coli* TOP10 cells were performed as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. The general scheme of cloning recombinant plasmid pET-28a(+)-PNP.

The obtained *E. coli* transformants were selected on a medium supplemented with the antibiotic-kanamycin. After transformation of competent *E. coli* TOP10 cells using pET-28a(+)-PNP, the resulting clones were screened by PCR and restriction analysis, which confirmed the presence of the insert (PNP gene - *deoD*) in the plasmid. The PCR results showed that the selected clones contained a DNA fragment of 728 bp (Fig. 3), which confirms the inclusion of the PNP-*deoD* gene insert in the recombinant plasmid pET-28a(+)-PNP.

Fig. 3. Gel electrophoresis (1%) of transformants. A- Recombinant pET-28a(+)-PNP; B- DNA marker; C- pET-28a(+) transfer vector (K-);

The comparative restriction analysis between the recombinant pET-28a(+)-PNP plasmid and the original pET-28a(+) vector using *EcoRI* at one restriction site showed a clear difference between the two plasmids (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Electrophoresis in 1% agarose gel of linearized recombinant plasmid pET-28a(+)-PNP and the transfer vector after restriction. A - pET-28a (+); B - pET-28a(+)-PNP; C - DNA Marker.

Conclusion. A novel recombinant DNA plasmid pET-28a(+)-PNP was cloned, which expresses recombinant purine nucleoside phosphorylase in *E. coli BL21 (DE3)* cells. The obtained recombinant PNP can provide cost-effective and large-scale production of modified nucleosides.

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